

ACNE AND METHODS OF ITS CORRECTION**Utayev Akbar Juraqulovich**

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Abstract: The task set before us to write this article was Assessing the prevalence of acne among young people, comparing the awareness of schoolchildren and students regarding acne , analyzing the impact of acne on the quality of life and psychosocial sphere of young people in different age categories. To achieve our goals and objectives, we analyzed and developed a questionnaire for assessing clinical and anamnestic data and psychosocial aspects of the subjects studied based on questions to assess the dermatological quality of life index. The study was open-label, simple and short-term. As a result, we came to the conclusion that the prevalence of acne in the age categories from 13 to 16 years and from 19 to 23 years did not differ significantly (43.8% and 46.4%, respectively). There was no gender advantage for male or female lesions (46% and 44.8%). Respondents in group II are more informed about this disease. Clinical manifestations of acne in the form of itching, burning and pain were more often noted by girls in group II. Compared to schoolchildren, students with acne are more susceptible to affective disorders and are 1.4 times more likely to report a decrease in self-esteem.

Key words: Acne , treatment, schoolchildren, depression, antibiotics, psychiatrists, clinical manifestations, analyzing, dermatological, depression.

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Аннотация: Целью написания данной статьи было изучение распространённости акне среди молодёжи, сравнение осведомлённости школьников и студентов относительно акне, а также анализ влияния акне на качество жизни и психосоциальную сферу молодёжи в разных возрастных категориях.

Для достижения поставленных задач был разработан и проанализирован опросник для оценки клиничко-анамнестических данных и психосоциальных аспектов испытуемых, основанный на вопросах для определения дерматологического индекса качества жизни. Исследование было открытым, простым и краткосрочным.

В результате было установлено, что распространённость акне в возрастных категориях от 13 до 16 лет и от 19 до 23 лет существенно не отличалась (43,8% и 46,4% соответственно). Половых различий в поражениях у мужчин и женщин также не отмечалось (46% и 44,8%). Респонденты из группы II (студенты) оказались более осведомлёнными о данном заболевании. Клинические проявления акне в виде зуда, жжения и боли чаще отмечались у девушек во второй группе.

По сравнению со школьниками, студенты с акне оказались более подвержены аффективным расстройствам и в 1,4 раза чаще сообщали о снижении самооценки.

Ключевые слова: акне, лечение, школьники, депрессия, антибиотики, психиатры, клинические проявления, анализ, дерматология.

INTRODUCTION

Acne (from ancient Greek ἀκμή - point, height, bloom), or acne is a long-term inflammatory skin disease that occurs when sebum clogs the hair follicle [3] [4]. Typical signs of this condition are comedones, pustules, oily skin, and possible scar formation[5][6][7]. The disease primarily affects the skin with a relatively large number of sebaceous glands, including the face, upper chest and back[8]. The resulting manifestations of the disease can lead to anxiety, low self-esteem and, in extreme cases, depression or suicidal thoughts[9][10], especially in adolescents. In 80% of cases, the main cause of acne is genetics[6]. The role of diet and smoking is unclear, and neither cleanliness nor exposure to sunlight appears to play a role [6][11][12]. In both sexes, androgen hormones appear to be part of the underlying mechanism, causing increased sebum production[13]. Another common factor is Cutibacterium overgrowth. acnes, which are present on the skin[14]. Treatments for acne include lifestyle changes, medications, and medical procedures. Reducing your intake of simple carbohydrates such as sugar may help[15]. Commonly used medications are applied directly to the affected skin, such as azelaic acid, benzoyl peroxide, and salicylic acid[16]. Antibiotics and retinoids are available in formulations that are applied to the skin and taken orally to treat acne [16]. However, antibiotic resistance may develop as a result of antibiotic therapy[17]. There are several types of oral contraceptives that help women fight acne [16]. Typically, health care providers use isotretinoin only to treat severe forms of acne due to the potentially higher risk of side effects[16][18]. Some of the medical community recommends early and more intensive treatment of acne to reduce the overall long-term impact on people[9].

Goals and objectives of the study: Assessing the prevalence of acne among young people, comparing the awareness of schoolchildren and students regarding acne, analyzing the impact of acne on the quality of life and psychosocial sphere of young people in different age categories.

Materials and methods. A questionnaire was developed to assess clinical and anamnestic data and psychosocial aspects of the subjects based on questions to assess the dermatological quality of life index. The study was open-label, simple and short-term. 614 people took part in the survey: Group I – schoolchildren aged 13 to 16 years (192 people), Group II – students aged 19 to 23 years (422 people). The results were collected through an anonymous online survey, a paper survey during an interactive lecture for students “Clear skin without acne” and while working in the dormitories of the Altai State Medical University.

Results 78 (40.6%) people in group I were aware of the problem of acne: 26 (30.6%) boys and 52 (48.6%) girls, in group II – 300 (71.1%) people: 99 (60.7%) boys and 201 (77.6%) girls. Of the respondents in group I, 84 (43.8%) people noted the presence of acne, among them 40 (47%) boys and 44 (41.1%) girls, from group II - 196 (46.4%) people: 74 boys (45.4%), girls – 122 (47.1%). Manifestations of acne in the form of itching, burning or soreness of the skin to varying degrees were noted by 159 (81.1%) students: 56 (75.7%) boys and 103 (84.4%) girls. Among schoolchildren, 59 (70.2%) people indicated the listed symptoms: 25 (62.5%) boys and 34 (77.3%) girls. Depression due to acne was indicated by 1 (1.2%) girl from group I and 17 (8.7%) people from group II: 1 (1.4%) boy and 16 (13.1%) girls. Anxiety was noted by 27 (32.1%) people in group I, of which 3 (7.5%) were boys and 24 (54.5%) girls. In group II, 90 (46%) people indicated anxiety: 13 (17.6%) boys and 77 (63.1%) girls. Increased irritability was noted by 26 (31%) respondents of group I: 16 (40%) boys and 10 (22.7%) girls and 62 (31.6%) respondents of group II: 37 (57%) boys and 25 (20.5%) girls. 30 (35.7%) people from the group of schoolchildren do not consider acne a problem: 21 (52.5%) boys and 9 (20.5%) girls and 27 (13.7%) people from the group of students: 23 (30.7%) boys and 4 (3.3%) girls. The negative impact of acne on self-

esteem (from slight to very strong) was detected in 151 (77%) students: 37 (50%) boys and 114 (93.4%) girls. Among schoolchildren, 45 (53.5%) people indicated a decrease in self-esteem due to acne : 23 (57.5%) boys and 22 (50%) girls. In group I, the influence of acne on leisure and social activity was noted by 18 (21.4%) people, of which 4 (10%) were boys and 14 (31.8%) girls. In group II – 67 (34.2%) people: 10 (13.6%) boys and 57 (46.7%) girls. The influence of acne on personal life was noted by 25 (29.8%) respondents of group I: 9 (22.5%) boys and 22 (50%) girls and 61 (31.1%) people of group II: 12 (16.3%)) boys and 49 (40.2%) girls.

Conclusions. The prevalence of acne in the age categories from 13 to 16 years and from 19 to 23 years did not differ significantly (43.8% and 46.4%, respectively). There was no gender advantage for male or female lesions (46% and 44.8%). Respondents in group II are more informed about this disease. Clinical manifestations of acne in the form of itching, burning and pain were more often noted by girls in group II. Compared to schoolchildren, students with acne are more susceptible to affective disorders and are 1.4 times more likely to report a decrease in self-esteem. Girls of both groups are most susceptible to anxiety and depression, boys - irritability. The influence of acne on leisure, social activity and personal life was noted by respondents of both groups; girls in group II more often noted this influence. The most vulnerable group in terms of nosogenic reactions are girls aged 19 to 23 years. Thus, the problem of the relationship between acne and psycho-emotional disorders is medical and social and relevant in modern dermatology and requires the organization of a system of interaction between dermatologists and psychiatrists.

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